

POLICY BRIEF

Climate Resilience and Education in Ghana

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Abbreviations and acronyms

EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
GES	Ghana Education Service
MESTI	Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation
MoE	Ministry of Education
NaSIA	National Schools Inspectorate Authority
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NADMO	National Disaster Management Organisation
NCCP	National Climate Change Policy

1. Background

Climate change is increasingly disrupting education in Ghana, whether through the direct impacts of extreme weather events on infrastructure and education delivery, or the indirect effects of mitigation responses, such as resource management or household-level behavioural changes. As a result, a multi-sectoral approach is required to mitigate against existing vulnerabilities and to build resilience in the education sector most effectively.

This policy brief presents a summary of key findings and recommendations from two recent studies: a landscape review which synthesises existing evidence on climate change and education in Ghana in order to highlight key vulnerabilities and potential solutions for building a climate-resilient education system ([↑D'Rozario et al., 2026](#)); and pilot research which assesses the impact of a 'cool roof' intervention on classroom temperature in the Northern Region ([↑Daltry et al., 2026](#)).

The brief aims to identify areas where further research, policy design, and programmatic development are needed to strengthen the climate resilience of Ghana's education sector. It is important to note that evidence is currently minimal: while general trends and recommendations may be drawn from studies in other contexts, it is critical to conduct further, context-specific research to support future decision-making. This brief provides a basis for building this evidence.

2. Summary of key findings

2.1. Climate hazards and their impact on education

Satellite data analysis and a structured review of existing academic and grey literature provide an overview of four climate hazards and the extent to which each impacts education in Ghana (see [↑D'Rozario et al., 2026](#), Section 4). A brief overview of each hazard is provided below.

2.1.1. Extreme heat

Satellite analysis: Exposure to extreme heat is a much greater risk in the northern regions of Ghana, with mean maximum daily temperatures exceeding 35°C for nearly a third of 2024.

Existing research: Two studies explore the effect of high temperatures on education in Ghana, focusing on children's thermal comfort and the impact of different school infrastructure materials. Current research,

however, does not investigate the relationship between temperature, thermal comfort, and learning outcomes.

2.1.2. Precipitation

Satellite analysis: Precipitation is heaviest in the east and the southwest of Ghana (particularly the Western Region), and driest in the north and the southeastern coastal belt (the Dahomey Gap). Recent trends also suggest consistently lower annual precipitation in the north, which has implications for precipitation-linked climatic events and education.

2.1.3. Flooding

Satellite analysis: A risk map of Ghana suggests that coastal areas and the Northern Region are particularly prone to flooding, due to a high concentration of rivers and the opening of the Bagre Dam.

Existing research: Two studies examine the impact of flooding on education, reporting damage to infrastructure and a reduction in short-term attendance and long-term enrolment at schools.

2.1.4. Drought

Satellite analysis: Much of Ghana is considered 'dryland', with the Dahomey Gap and the north most vulnerable to drought. Analysis also indicates that the central and southern areas are 'drying out' more rapidly than other regions, relative to the long-term 'climate normal'.

Existing research: No literature examines the impact of drought on education in Ghana; research in comparable contexts suggests mixed impact, often relating to whether a school feeding programme is offered.

2.2. Building climate resilience: Key stakeholders

The following stakeholders are, or could be, well positioned to support the development of climate-resilience initiatives in education in Ghana. For a full overview of each stakeholder's remit, please refer to [↑D'Rozario et al. \(2026\)](#) (Section 5.1).

- **The Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology and Innovation (MESTI)** leads policy development for the environment, science, technology, and innovation, coordinating intersectoral work for climate action and sustainable development, including the delivery of the National Climate Change Policy (NCCP) and its financing through the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC).

- **The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)** sits under MESTI as the technical body responsible for coordinating climate initiatives, compliance with climate resilience policies (including disaster risk reduction and the NCCP) and delivering public education on the environment.
- **The Ministry of Education (MoE)** is responsible for coordinating education planning, budgeting, and delivery, including infrastructure improvements.
- **The Ghana Education Service (GES)** is the lead body that implements and monitors education policy, manages curriculum reforms, integrates climate change into curricula, and trains teachers.
- **The National Disaster Management Organisation (NADMO)** has a mandate to manage disasters and emergencies, and largely focuses on response and relief efforts.
- **The World Bank** provides large-scale funding for climate and disaster resilience initiatives and infrastructure.
- **The Gower Street Trust** provides philanthropic funding for climate education innovation and partnerships.
- **UNICEF Ghana** works to promote children's well-being, with a strong focus on water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH), education, and safety.
- **NGOs** — including CAMFED Ghana, Green for Change Ghana, and the Rights & Advocacy Initiatives Network (RAIN) deliver climate-resilience and education initiatives; EduSpots & Climate Education Community of Practice (CECOP) is a coalition of 10 Ghanaian NGOs focused on providing complementary climate education for schools.

2.3. Building climate resilience: Existing policy and initiatives

There are few specific references to education within existing climate change policy, nor standards against which adaptation efforts can be measured, with the main focus on climate change education rather than building resilience:

- **The National Climate Change Policy (NCCP)** provides a comprehensive overview of adaptation efforts, but in terms of

education, its main focus is climate change education; there is no focus on resilience-building for education, nor on the role of the MoE in delivering climate-resilient systems ([↑MESTI, 2013](#)).

- **The National Schools Inspectorate Authority** mentions the need for school roofs to be “made of a safe material that doesn’t generate too much heat” ([↑NaSIA, 2022, p. 21](#)) and that school compounds “must not be flood prone” ([↑NaSIA, 2022, p. 20](#)), but there are no standards or other thresholds to support adherence to these objectives.
- **The National Climate Change and Green Economy Learning Strategy** has led to curricula revisions to include climate change indicators (usually in science subjects), led by MESTI and the EPA, in partnership with the GES ([↑MESTI, 2016](#)).
- **Action for Climate Empowerment (ACE)**, delivered through the EPA, also focuses on climate change education, aiming to encourage behavioural change and community action ([↑UNESCO & UNFCCC, 2016](#)).

While a few other programmes related to climate resilience through education exist (see [↑D'Rozario et al., 2026, Section 5.2](#)), there is limited evidence on the effectiveness or impact of these initiatives. Research does suggest, however, that there are opportunities to strengthen resilience through the existing education system ([↑D'Rozario et al., 2026, Section 5.3](#)). These include:

- Developing cross-cutting infrastructural resilience.
- Improving disaster risk reduction for education.
- Emphasising an action-focused approach within existing climate change education.

2.4. Building infrastructural resilience to extreme heat

Existing research indicates a need to enhance the resilience of schools against extreme heat, especially in the north of Ghana:

- Mean maximum daily temperatures exceeded 35°C for nearly a third of 2024 in the Upper West, Upper East, North East, Savannah, Northern and Bono East regions ([↑D'Rozario et al., 2026, Section 4.1](#)).

- Evidence from other contexts suggests a negative causal link between high temperatures and learning outcomes ([↑Graff Zivin et al., 2018](#); [↑Park et al., 2021](#); [↑Wargoeki et al., 2019](#)).
- Small-scale research in Ghana suggests that school infrastructure can exacerbate high outdoor temperatures ([↑Amankwaa et al., 2025](#)):
 - Metal-roofed classrooms can be up to 5.9°C warmer than outdoors.
 - Concrete roofs are, on average, the coolest roof type, especially when outdoor temperatures exceed 32°C.
 - Plywood ceilings might be cooler than metal-roofed classrooms without ceilings.

A preliminary mapping of school infrastructure in Ghana's Northern Region suggests a need for adaptation strategies to mitigate the negative impact of existing infrastructure and extreme heat on learning (see [↑Daltry et al., 2026](#)). Across 50 surveyed schools in Tamale Metro and Kumbungu districts:

- All surveyed school roofs were metal, either galvanised steel (40.5%), aluzinc (32.4%), or aluminium (21.6%).
- Classroom temperatures in schools with galvanised steel roofs were 0.40°C warmer on average than those in schools with other roof types.
- Classroom temperatures in metal-roofed classrooms with ceilings were 0.70°C cooler on average than those without ceilings.
- Direct sunlight strikes 98% of metal roofs.
- 64% of school leaders reported that extreme heat had affected education in the past academic year (the highest among reports of the impact of climate hazards, ahead of strong winds [46%] and heavy rainfall [28%]).
- 24% of school leaders reported that lower primary classes sometimes take place outdoors due to high classroom temperatures.

2.5. Pilot research: A 'cool roof' intervention

Research indicates that painting metal roofs with specialised white paint can reduce indoor temperatures ([↑Androutsopoulos et al., 2017](#); [↑Garg et al., 2016](#)); [↑Proctor, 2022](#); A pilot study across 20 schools in the Northern

Region investigated the viability of this approach as a “retrofit” intervention to reduce classroom temperatures ([↑Daltry et al., 2026](#)). Results suggest that:

- Specialised white paint (with heat-reflective qualities) reduces indoor temperatures by over 2°C, and its effectiveness increases during peak sunlight hours; however, this cooling effect lessens to ~1.7°C when considering only term-time hours, highlighting the heating impact of a full classroom.
- Basic white paint (without heat-reflective qualities) can reduce indoor temperature by over 1°C, but its effectiveness reduces during peak sunlight hours.
- The effectiveness of white paint is statistically significant on all types of metal roofs.
- While specialised white paint significantly reduced temperatures across all classrooms, the cooling effect of the paint was 1.6°C lower in classrooms with ceilings, as ceilings were potentially already contributing to temperature reduction.
- Although white paint significantly reduced classroom temperatures, it did not significantly impact relative humidity during term-time. This may limit its impact on children’s thermal comfort.

A ‘cool roof’ intervention, therefore, holds promise for mitigating the negative impact of existing school infrastructure on classroom temperatures. However, two main limitations should be considered:

1. It is unknown whether a ~2°C reduction in classroom temperature can improve learning outcomes in a region that experiences sustained extreme heat, even though the intervention did not appear to affect classroom relative humidity significantly. The question of “how hot is too hot for learning in Ghana?” therefore remains unanswered.
2. The cost-effectiveness of a ‘cool roof’ intervention is also yet to be determined, especially compared to the impact of other retrofit interventions on key education metrics.

3. Future directions

Evidence on “what works” in relation to climate resilience strategies for education in Ghana remains preliminary. The recommendations below (drawn from [↑D'Rozario et al. \(2026\)](#) and [↑Daltry et al. \(2026\)](#)) aim to

encourage multi-sectoral coordination and evidence-building, so that future initiatives can be grounded in contextually relevant data and ensure alignment among key stakeholders.

3.1. Policy for climate-resilient education

Education needs to have a defined focus within Ghana's existing climate change policy and resilience initiatives. Cross-sectoral policy and coordination are required both to mitigate potential risks to children's learning and leverage opportunities for community-led resilience initiatives. Recommendations include the following.

3.1.1. Establish specific roles and responsibilities for the MoE and relevant education agencies within the NCCP, alongside those of the EPA and MESTI

Cross-sectoral coordination is required to ensure a comprehensive approach to climate resilience. Defining the roles of the MoE and relevant agencies is a starting point for ensuring that the NCCP and related policies can explicitly support education (see also [3.2.1](#)).

3.1.2. Develop clear targets and a mapping tool, aligned with the Basic Education Infrastructure Framework, to aid implementation of National Schools Inspectorate Authority guidelines

Standards should be aligned for both the construction of new school buildings and the assessment of existing school infrastructure to aid adaptation measures. Clear numerical targets should be set for climate-related metrics, including the target thermal range for classrooms (to support optimal environments for learning, see Section [3.3.1](#)) and a clear definition of what constitutes 'flood-prone' (to support anticipatory action initiatives, see Section [3.1.3](#)). Establishing specific metrics will provide a means for systematic measurement and compliance. The development of these standards should take place alongside the adoption of the recently revised Basic Education Infrastructure Framework to ensure alignment between the MoE, the National Schools Inspectorate Authority (NaSIA), and other relevant agencies. All standards and resources for assessing existing infrastructure should also be made easily accessible and actionable for district-level education officials, for implementation alongside existing Environmental Compliance guidelines.

3.1.3. Enhance NADMO's capacity to enable a shift towards anticipatory action alongside reactive disaster response

This will require the development of specific anticipatory action frameworks and financing mechanisms. Crucially, such frameworks should incorporate education-focused strategies (e.g., action plans for learning continuity during floods) to reduce the disruption caused by climate hazards and support learning continuity.

3.1.4. Strengthen the climate change education curriculum and pedagogy towards an action-focused approach

This will require embedding action-focused teaching within existing teacher professional development. Additionally, ensuring that curriculum and teaching can be contextualised to draw on local climatic patterns and experiences may support more meaningful community-level knowledge and action.

3.2. Climate financing to support education resilience

An increased global focus on climate financing to mitigate the negative effects of climate change, especially in the low- and middle-income countries, presents opportunities to support education resilience in Ghana. Leveraging such funds, however, requires a central role for the MoE and relevant agencies in the application for and implementation of such funding, especially when financing is multi-sectoral. Recommendations include the following.

3.2.1. Ensure that education is a specific focus within Ghana's Nationally Determined Contribution

This is required to ensure that climate funds are allocated to adaptation efforts that support resilience building in education. Any cross-sectoral funds should also explicitly include education targets.

3.2.2. Leverage climate financing for multi-sectoral projects to service education-related initiatives

For example, climate financing invested in public infrastructure building projects should include schools as part of its wider remit.

3.2.3. Establish incentives to increase investment in climate financing from the private sector

This is an area which requires further investigation, but offers an opportunity to leverage a range of funds to support both economic and social development.

3.3. Research to support evidence-based decisions

Further research is needed to explicitly determine the national- and regional-level impacts of climate change and extreme weather events on education in Ghana, as well as the effectiveness of different mitigation efforts. In particular, without establishing the causal relationship between specific hazards and learning outcomes, it will be challenging to determine the comparative cost-effectiveness of various response mechanisms and aid evidence-based decision-making. Recommendations include the following.

3.3.1. Determine the temperature threshold(s) at which exposure to extreme heat begins to affect learning in Ghana negatively

While analysis clearly shows exposure to high temperatures, it is crucial to understand at what temperatures thermal comfort and learning performance are affected, given that regular exposure to extreme heat suggests this value is likely higher in Ghana than in other contexts where research has been conducted. Determining these specific thresholds is a vital precursor to designing any heat-reduction interventions or thermal regulations for indoor spaces.

3.3.2. Rigorously investigate what educational impacts are associated with different types of school infrastructure

Specifically, it is important to assess whether particular materials (including metal-roofed classrooms) are significantly correlated with poor learning outcomes and attendance, and to what extent this can be mitigated by adapting infrastructure.

3.3.3. Analyse the cost-effectiveness of ‘cool roof’ paint and other retrofit interventions

Alongside establishing the relationship between different roof materials and learning outcomes (see also Section [3.2.2.](#)), further evidence is required to understand which retrofit interventions can 1) have the greatest cooling

effect, 2) contribute the most towards improved learning outcomes, and 3) be delivered at the lowest cost. This would allow a full cost-effectiveness analysis to determine appropriate infrastructure standards.

3.3.4. Commission long-term rigorous research to determine the differences and interactions between rapid-onset and slow-onset climate crises and their impacts on education

Research on these issues should particularly focus on the northern regions of Ghana that are most exposed to both flooding and drought. Testing how these variables interact and how short- and long-term climatic impacts affect learning outcomes is critical to fully understanding the risks associated with specific climatic hazards.

3.3.5. Examine the potential of Ghana's existing School Feeding Programme as a strategy for mitigating the impacts of climate hazards on education, particularly during drought

The literature suggests that access to food can improve access to education in drought conditions. Evaluating the impact of the School Feeding Programme may therefore be a sensible first step towards building evidence on drought response efforts in Ghana, given the comparative ease of scaling existing initiatives if proven impactful.

3.3.6. Assess trends in precipitation, attendance rates, and other seasonal variables

Currently, it is challenging to determine whether rainfall has a causal impact on school attendance or whether other factors, such as seasonal changes in agricultural practices, are stronger determinants. Further research to establish the relationship between these metrics will aid the design of school-level initiatives to boost attendance.

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